

DETERMINANTS AFFECTING READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS AMONG STUDENTS OF ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM

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Determinants Affecting Reading Comprehension Skills among Students of Alternative Learning System

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate different factors affecting the reading comprehension skills of the students in Alternative Learning System of Lugait Central School. The respondents of this study were 40 females and 60 males. A survey was conducted by using a questionnaire for information gathering about different factors relating to the reading performance of the students and the Phil-IRI assessment tool to assess their comprehension level. This study was conducted to the Junior High School students enrolled in the Alternative Learning System at Lugait Central School during the school year 2023-2024. The study used the descriptive-correlational research design. The results of the study revealed that 'the socio-economic status and different determinants have no significant effect to the reading performance of the students but in the marital status the widow exhibited a significant positive correlation with the reading comprehension skills compared to the other marital status. In the context of the reading comprehension, it was found out that the comprehension level of the students' majority fell into frustration and instructional levels indicated a need for targeted interventions which aimed at improving foundational reading skills.

Keywords: *reading performance, Alternative Learning System, Phil-IRI Assessment, and comprehension level*

Introduction

The ability to read acts as a crucial factor in developing confidence and a good self-image among learners. Poor readers often have low opinions of themselves and their abilities. They can perform poorly in other subjects because they cannot read and cannot understand the reading material. Often the reader tends to give up (Islam & Siddik 2020). One of the most important foundations for students' confidence and positive self-image development is their ability to read. People with strong reading abilities are better able to interact with their environment, obtain information, and communicate efficiently. On the other hand, those who struggle with reading could have negative self-perceptions since it might make it difficult for them to understand what they read and difficult to participate in different social and academic activities. Building excellent reading skills is crucial for students' academic performance as well as for developing a sense of competence and self-worth.

According to DepEd Memorandum No. 173, 2019 as the result of previous national assessments revealing that learners still need improvement in literacy skills, DepEd's 3Bs initiative encourages offices from central to division level and schools to intensify their advocacies for reading to make every learner a reader at their grade level and capacitate teachers to become effective reading instructors.

Reading comprehension is one of the most complex cognitive activities in which humans engage, making it difficult to teach, measure, and research (Elleman & Oslund 2019). Among the many different cognitive tasks that people perform, reading comprehension stands out as being especially complex and difficult. It requires a variety of talents due to the intricate process of deciphering written language, obtaining meaning, and synthesizing information. Teachers who are trying to teach reading comprehension may find it challenging since it involves more than just word recognition; it also involves higher-level cognitive processes. Evaluating reading comprehension is equally complicated and necessitates a thorough assessment that extends beyond conventional literacy tests. Furthermore, linguistics and psychology are among the fields that have studied this cognitive process, indicating the necessity for an interdisciplinary approach. Understanding and successfully resolving the challenges of reading comprehension remain critical in education and research, as it is a critical component of literacy and academic success.

Reading is one of the essential components of the English language. Countries that use English as a second language (ESL) sometimes have difficulties in reading and comprehension (Mohammad & Hasbi 2021). Some students experienced anxiety and disinterest during English class because they were unable to read and comprehend simple words due to a lack of exposure to the language, inadequate instruction, and factors affecting the students' reading comprehension, such as caring for their families and having children, lack of phonemic awareness, alphabetic understanding, vocabulary fluency, prior knowledge, engagement, and interest. When participating in group reading activities, they will just rely on their seatmates, or they will always read along with their seatmates even when they are unfamiliar with a particular term. Getting back their interest, the researcher would like to know what are their strength and weaknesses that affect their reading comprehension skills. Here, they work individually in which they will be given time to read the survey questionnaire and answer it in a given time.

Furthermore, students can express their weaknesses and strengths or factors that affect their reading skills by answering the survey questionnaire and reading a selection to identify their comprehension level from the Phil-IRI assessment tool. The major impact of this study is to determine the factors that affect the reading comprehension of the students. As an effective teacher, students will know how to read the basic words so that it is easy for them to read the paragraph by determining their strengths.

The main objective of the study was to determine the factors affecting reading comprehension among students of the Alternative Learning System in Lugait Central School. The study was conducted in the third quarter of the S.Y. 2023-2024. The researcher one year as a volunteer teacher in the Alternative Learning System, also teaching in a private school for one year, and a third time as a Substitute Teacher in a Public School. She has the eagerness to make appropriate adjustments for learners of different learning backgrounds by making use of different learning styles that will suit the needs of learners. Also, the researchers wanted to have fulfillment in her career in which she could contribute to the educational system.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the determinants affecting reading comprehension among ALS students in Lugait District during the SY 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-economic profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. parent's occupation;
 - 1.4. monthly parents' income;
 - 1.5. marital status;
 - 1.6. grade level; and
 - 1.7. occupation?
2. What are the determinants that affect the reading comprehension skills of the respondents?
 - 2.1. learning preferences;
 - 2.2. motivation;
 - 2.3. attitude;
 - 2.4. teaching techniques;
 - 2.5. texts; and
 - 2.6. environments?
3. What is the reading comprehension of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-economic profile and the determinants that affect the reading comprehension skills of the respondents?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-economic profile and the reading comprehension skills of the respondents?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the determinants that affect the reading comprehension and the reading comprehension skills of the respondents?
7. What action plan for students can be formulated based on the result of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive-correlational research design. This design involves collecting data on multiple variables of interest and examining the degree of association between them, providing a snapshot of existing relationships in a naturalistic setting. It is particularly useful for investigating patterns and trends in a given phenomenon, offering insights into the strength and direction of connections between variables without implying causation.

Descriptive research was used to describe the socio-economic profile and the determinants that affect reading comprehension of Junior High School students of Alternative Learning System. They were given a survey questionnaire. It is also correlational research since the socio-economic profile of the respondents is correlated to the reading comprehension skills of the respondents in terms of language and literacy.

In the context of determinants affecting reading comprehension, a descriptive-correlational design was applied by collecting data on various potential influencing factors and examining their relationships without manipulating any variables. The researcher gathered information on determinants such as vocabulary proficiency, reading fluency, prior knowledge, and reading habits among a sample of participants. Through statistical analysis, the study revealed the nature and strength of correlations between these determinants and reading comprehension scores of the respondents. This approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between different elements and their impact on reading comprehension abilities, without introducing experimental interventions.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Junior High School students of the Alternative Learning System at the Community Learning Center of Lugait Central School, enrolled during the school year 2023-2024. The researcher used simple random sampling wherein respondents were selected randomly in the Learner Information System. One hundred forty-two (142) students were enrolled in the S.Y. 2023-2024 and Forty (40) females and sixty (60) males were chosen through random sampling that randomly picks on the Learner Information System with a total of 100 respondents.

Instrument

This study used an adopted questionnaire where the researcher identified the most relevant questions. In the first part, the respondents filled in some personal questions, the second part was the determinants affecting reading comprehension and the third part was the Reading Comprehension. The survey questionnaire was taken from the article entitled “An Analysis of Factors Affecting the English Reading Comprehension of Mattayomsuksa Students in Amphur Mueang, Lampang Province” was used by Sajeerat Wutthisingchai and Peter James Stopps (2015). The Reading Comprehension selection was taken in the Phil-IRI assessment tool (2018).

The validation process culminated in a survey questionnaire that demonstrated high content and construct validity. The resulting instrument was a robust and reliable tool for data collection, providing a strong foundation for the analysis and findings of this study. The meticulous validation procedures reinforced the credibility and accuracy of the data. It contributed to the quality of the research within the context of exploring reading proficiency among ALS students.

Procedure

The researcher personally conducted the study and facilitated the gathering of data. The data-gathering process was done in this manner. The researcher sent out letters to the SDS, PSDIC, the Principal, and the District ALS Focal Person of the school where the study was conducted. Next, the researcher sent first the letter to the respondents, and after the respondents voluntarily allowed the conduct of the study, the researcher presented the survey questionnaire to the students. They were given time to read and answer the questions. Students answered the survey questionnaire which is the first part is their socio-economic profile age, sex, parents' income and occupation, marital status, grade level, and occupation.

The second part was the determinants affecting reading comprehension evaluation in which the respondents put a checkmark in each item which described their behavior towards the instructional materials based on a scale of 1 to 5 where 5 strongly agree, 4 Agree, 3 Neither Disagree nor Disagree, 2 Disagree and 1 strongly disagree. Lastly, the respondents and the researcher had one on one oral reading of the given selection. After reading, they answered the following questions based on the selection they read. For the conduct of one-on-one oral reading with the respondents, it took seven (7) hours per day and it started last February 19, 2024 until February 26, 2024 to finish the oral reading with the respondents. The results of the survey were collected and submitted to the accredited statistician of the school.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented.

For problem 1, frequency and percentage were used to describe the socio-economic profiles of the respondents in terms of age, gender, parents' income and occupation, marital status, grade level, and occupation.

For problem 2, mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to describe the determinants that affect the reading comprehension of the respondents.

For problem 3, frequency and percentage were used to describe the reading comprehension of the respondents.

For problem 4, the Point-Biserial Correlation coefficient (r-value) and associated p-values were used to determine the significant relationship between the socioeconomic profile and the determinants that affect the reading comprehension skills of the respondents.

For problem 5, the Point-Biserial Correlation coefficient (r-value) and associated p-values were used to determine the significant relationship between the socioeconomic profile and the reading comprehension skills of the respondents.

For problem 6, the Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) and corresponding p-values were used to determine the determinants that affect the reading comprehension and the reading comprehension skills of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered following the sequence of the specific questions posed by this study.

Problem 1: What is the socio-economic profile of respondents in terms of age, sex, parent's occupation, monthly parents' income, marital status, grade level, and occupation?

Table 2. Age of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below-20	35	35.0
21-40	51	51.0
41-above	14	14.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents based on their age in a survey or study. The data was categorized into three age groups: Below-20, 21-40, and 41-above. The table indicated that the majority of respondents, constituting 51.0%, fell within the age range of

21 to 40 years, while 14.0% were 41 years old and above had the lowest frequency.

According to Jia (2022), learners of different ages have different learning characteristics, and there was a close relationship between the starting age of language learners and their English mastery ability. In other words, the language learners, whose starting age is younger, have more advantages than those whose starting age is older. Individuals of varying ages exhibit distinct learning characteristics, and the commencement age of language acquisition closely correlates with their proficiency in English.

Table 3. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	60	60.0
Female	40	40.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 shows the sex distribution among the respondents in a study. The data was categorized into two groups: male and female. The table revealed that 60.0% of the respondents were identified as males, while 40.0% identified as females.

Reilly, Neumann, and Andrews, (2018), sex difference that has been discovered points to a possible advantage for women in domains related to verbal understanding and language proficiency.

Table 4. *Parents' Occupation of the Respondents*

<i>Parents' Occupation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Farmer	42	42.0
Construction Worker	38	38.0
Vendor	17	17.0
OFW	3	3.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 provides an overview of the parents' occupations of the respondents in a survey or study, categorizing the data into four main groups: Farmer, Construction Worker, Vendor, and OFW (Overseas Filipino Worker). The table indicated that the most common parent occupation among the respondents was farming, with 42.0% of the participants having parents engaged in agricultural activities, while Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) represented the smallest percentage at 3.0%.

Parental occupation is the most determining factor of generating income which affected the overall development of young wards especially their academic development and progress (Shah & Hussain, 2021).

Table 5. *Monthly Family Income of the Respondents*

<i>Monthly Family Income</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Less than 20,000	100	100.0
More than 20,000	0	0.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 presents the monthly family income distribution among the respondents in a survey or study. The data was categorized into two groups: Less than 20,000 and more than 20,000. Strikingly, the table revealed that 100% of the respondents reported a monthly family income of less than 20,000, with no respondents falling into the category of more than 20,000. This information underscored the economic circumstances of the surveyed population, indicating that all respondents had family incomes below the 20,000 thresholds.

According to Shah and Hussain (2021), a family's financial resources can directly impact a child's academic development. Parents with higher levels of education and professional backgrounds may be more equipped to provide academic support to their children. They can assist with homework, engage in discussions about reading materials, and encourage a positive attitude towards learning.

Table 6. *Marital Status of the Respondents*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Married	57	57.0
Single	41	41.0
Widow	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6 reveals the marital status distribution of the respondents in a survey or study. The data was categorized into three groups: married, single, and widow. The table indicated that the majority of respondents constituting 57.0%, were married, and a small percentage, 2.0%, fell into the category of widow. This information offered valuable insights into the marital status diversity within the surveyed population, illustrating the prevalence of married individuals and the significant representation of singles.

According to Ndayambaje et al. (2020), married people were happier than singles, divorced, and widowers. Highly educated people were happier and satisfied than those who were less educated.

Table 7. Grade Level of the Respondents

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Grade 7	58	58.0
Grade 8	29	29.0
Grade 9	13	13.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 7 provides an overview of the grade levels of the respondents in a survey or study, categorizing the data into three groups: Grade 7, Grade 8, and Grade 9. The table revealed that the majority of respondents, comprising 58.0%, were in Grade 7 and Grade 9 accounts for 13.0%. This information highlighted the distribution of respondents across different grade levels, showcasing a higher representation of Grade 7 students compared to Grades 8 and 9.

Reading skills must be developed among our learners in preparation for the higher stages of their studies (Torres, 2019). Students with varying reading levels could work together to create a dynamic and encouraging learning environment that promoted academic progress and growth for all involved.

Table 8. Occupation of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Farmer	28	28.0
Housewife	43	43.0
Construction Worker	15	15.0
Student	14	14.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 8 displays the distribution of occupations among the respondents in a survey or study, categorizing the data into four main groups: farmer, housewife, construction worker, and student. The table indicated that the highest percentage of respondents, comprising 43.0% were identified as housewives, and 14.0% was the lowest percentage that fell into student. This information provided insights into the diverse occupational backgrounds of the surveyed population, showcasing a significant representation of housewives and a mix of other occupations.

Working while studying is driven fundamentally by budgetary need: to cover setbacks in different types of understudy bolster; to top up salary to give a superior understudy understanding, or to help towards future objectives (Abenoja, 2019).

Assessing global awareness of reading comprehension among students involves considering various factors such as educational policies, literacy rates, cultural attitudes toward education, and available resources for teaching reading skills. By considering these factors, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can gain a better understanding of global awareness of students' reading performance and identify strategies to promote literacy and improve reading outcomes for all learners.

Problem 2: What are the factors that affect reading comprehension skills of the respondents?

Table 9. Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension Skills of the Respondents in terms of Learning Preferences

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Using the pictures	4.87	.34	Strongly Agree
2. Using speed reading	3.35	1.35	Neither Agree nor Disagree
3. Reading frequently	3.56	.82	Agree
4. Finding the keywords	4.77	.45	Strongly Agree
5. Finding the main ideas	4.59	.74	Strongly Agree
6. Questioning to review schemata	4.31	1.01	Agree
7. Using grammar and structure knowledge	4.62	.30	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	4.30	.30	Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.50–4.49, Agree; 4.50–5.00, Strongly Agree

Table 9 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) of respondents' perceptions regarding various indicators that determined their reading comprehension skills in terms of learning preferences. The mean values, representing the average response for each indicator, along with the standard deviations, indicating the degree of variability in the responses, offered insights into the participants' opinions.

The highest mean scores were observed for indicators such as "Using the pictures" (Mean=4.87), "Finding the keywords" (Mean=4.77), "Finding the main ideas" (Mean=4.59), and "Using grammar and structure knowledge" (Mean=4.62). These high mean scores, coupled with low standard deviations, suggested a strong consensus among respondents, with the majority expressing a "Strongly Agree" sentiment toward these learning preferences.

On the other hand, "Using speed reading" (Mean=3.35) and "Questioning to review schemata" (Mean=4.31) received lower mean scores, indicating more varied opinions, especially for the former, which fell in the "Neither Agree nor Disagree" range. The overall mean for the total measure was 4.30, with a low standard deviation of 0.30, suggesting a generally consistent agreement among

respondents regarding the factors affecting their reading comprehension skills.

Implications of these findings could be significant for educators and curriculum developers. The strong agreement on certain indicators, such as using pictures, finding keywords, and utilizing grammar and structure knowledge, suggested that these methods were well-received and may enhance reading comprehension skills. However, the lower agreement on speed reading and questioning to review schemata indicated a need for further exploration or adaptation of teaching strategies in these areas.

Good word reading skills are one of the most critical skills required for effective comprehension of written material by Joseph (2018). It was said that strong word reading comprehension is fundamental to effective written material comprehension because it formed the basis of the reading process as a whole. Teachers should provide differentiated instructional materials for the diverse learners to cope up the reading gaps.

Table 10. *Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension Skills of the Respondents in terms of Motivation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Love in reading	3.60	.83	Agree
2. An interest in the reading text	3.95	1.10	Agree
3. Gaining better scores in the test	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
4. Gaining more knowledge	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
5. Gaining the praises/nominations/awards	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
6. Going to study abroad	2.23	1.12	Disagree
7. A requirement to relate or involve with native speakers	4.89	.31	Strongly Agree
8. A requirement to succeed in future career	4.41	.84	Agree
Total Measure	4.26	.27	Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.50–4.49, Agree; 4.50–5.00, Strongly Agree

Table 10 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) for indicators related to the motivation of respondents in terms of determinants affecting their reading comprehension skills. The mean values provided an insight into the average response for each indicator, and the standard deviations indicated the degree of variability in the responses.

The highest mean scores were observed for indicators such as "Gaining better scores in the test" (Mean=5.00), "Gaining more knowledge" (Mean=5.00), and "Gaining the praises/nominations/awards" (Mean=5.00). These maximum mean scores, coupled with zero standard deviations, suggested unanimous agreement, with all respondents indicating a "Strongly Agree" sentiment towards these motivations. This implied that achieving better test scores, acquiring knowledge, and receiving praise, nominations, or awards strongly motivated respondents in enhancing their reading comprehension skills.

On the other hand, "Going to study abroad" received a lower mean score of 2.23, indicating a disagreement among respondents regarding this particular motivation. The variability was reflected in the high standard deviation of 1.12 for this indicator.

The overall mean for the total measure was 4.26, with a low standard deviation of 0.27, suggesting a consistent agreement among respondents regarding the motivational factors influencing their reading comprehension skills.

The implications of these findings for educators and policymakers were significant. The strong agreement on motivations related to academic success, knowledge acquisition, and recognition indicated that these factors played a crucial role in driving students' interest and effort in improving reading comprehension. Understanding these motivations can help educators tailor their teaching methods and curriculum to align with students' aspirations, fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment.

The pupils' perception of their ability or self-confidence was the central mediating construct of their achievement strivings in reading (National Academy of Sciences, 2018). The student's achievement is greatly influenced by their self-perception of their abilities and confidence, especially when it comes to reading.

Table 11. *Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension Skills of the Respondents in terms of Attitude*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Enjoyment in reading	4.50	.85	Strongly Agree
2. Teaching technique preferences	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
3. Confidences in reading skills more than other skills	3.51	.77	Agree
4. Pride in oneself to be able to read other languages	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
5. Excitement of knowing other cultures, tradition and lifestyle from reading	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
6. A requirement to know more of the reading story	4.96	.20	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	4.66	.19	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.50–4.49, Agree; 4.50–5.00, Strongly Agree

Table 11 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) for indicators related to the attitude of respondents in terms of determinants affecting their reading comprehension skills. The mean values provided insights into the average response for each indicator, and the

standard deviations indicated the degree of variability in the responses.

The highest mean scores were observed for indicators such as "Teaching technique preferences" (Mean=5.00), "Pride in oneself to be able to read other languages" (Mean=5.00), "Excitement of knowing other cultures, tradition, and lifestyle from reading" (Mean=5.00), and "A requirement to know more of the reading story" (Mean=4.96). These maximum mean scores, coupled with zero standard deviations, indicated unanimous agreement, with all respondents expressing a "Strongly Agree" sentiment towards these aspects of attitude. This implied that respondents highly value effective teaching techniques, take pride in their ability to read other languages, find excitement in learning about different cultures through reading, and recognize the importance of fully understanding a reading story.

The overall mean for the total measure was 4.66, with a low standard deviation of 0.19, suggesting a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the attitude-related factors influencing their reading comprehension skills.

The implications of these findings were crucial for educators and curriculum designers. The strong agreement on factors such as teaching technique preferences and the appreciation of diverse cultural perspectives through reading suggested that incorporating innovative and engaging teaching methods, along with diverse reading materials, can significantly enhance students' attitudes toward reading. Recognizing and leveraging these positive attitudes can contribute to the development of effective reading comprehension skills. Additionally, understanding students' pride in multilingual abilities emphasized the importance of fostering a positive language-learning environment. Overall, aligning teaching strategies with these positive attitudes could create a more enriching and motivating learning experience for students.

DepEd Order (DO) No. 8, s. 2013, teachers strengthened their abilities and skills and adapted new techniques to help their students get positive outcomes to address the reading and learning gaps, achieve expected competencies, and help instill the love of reading and learning.

Table 12. *Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension Skills of the respondents in terms of Teaching Techniques*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. A technique of word-guessing from context clues	4.65	.76	Strongly Agree
2. A technique of setting the reading purposes	4.55	.81	Strongly Agree
3. A technique of skimming the text before reading	4.96	.20	Strongly Agree
4. A technique of asking questions before, during and after reading	4.35	1.02	Agree
5. A technique of word-guessing from root, prefix and suffix	4.98	.14	Strongly Agree
6. A technique of grammar and structure analysis for predicting the tone of the story	4.74	.97	Strongly Agree
7. A technique of building awareness of student's reading strategies	4.45	.89	Agree
8. A technique of summarizing the outline of reading story	4.88	.36	Strongly Agree
9. A technique of identifying facts and opinion of reading story	4.45	.76	Agree
10. A technique of finding the major and minor details of reading story	4.07	.87	Agree
Total Measure	4.61	.20	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.50–4.49, Agree; 4.50–5.00, Strongly Agree

Table 12 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) for indicators related to teaching techniques and their impact on the reading comprehension skills of the respondents. The mean values offered insights into the average response for each teaching technique, and the standard deviations indicated the degree of variability in the responses.

The highest mean scores were observed for several teaching techniques, including "A technique of skimming the text before reading" (Mean=4.96), "A technique of word-guessing from root, prefix, and suffix" (Mean=4.98), "A technique of summarizing the outline of the reading story" (Mean=4.88), and "A technique of grammar and structure analysis for predicting the tone of the story" (Mean=4.74). These high mean scores, coupled with low standard deviations, suggested a strong consensus among respondents, with the majority expressing a "Strongly Agree" sentiment towards these teaching techniques. This indicated that these techniques were highly valued and perceived as effective by the respondents for enhancing reading comprehension skills.

While "A technique of asking questions before, during, and after reading" and "A technique of finding the major and minor details of the reading story" received slightly lower mean scores, they still fell within the "Agree" range, suggesting general agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of these techniques.

The overall mean for the total measure was 4.61, with a low standard deviation of 0.20, indicating a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the positive impact of teaching techniques on their reading comprehension skills.

The implications of these findings were significant for educators. The strong agreement on various teaching techniques underscored the importance of incorporating these methods into reading instruction. Educators can leverage skimming, word-guessing strategies, summarization, and grammar and structure analysis to enhance students' comprehension abilities. Additionally, understanding the slightly lower agreement on certain techniques provided insight into areas where educators may need to focus more attention or adapt

their teaching methods to better align with student preferences and perceived effectiveness. Overall, aligning teaching techniques with students' preferences and recognizing their effectiveness can contribute to a more engaging and successful reading comprehension learning experience.

Reading is one of the four language skills required when the students learn the target. Both English teachers and students need to improve and master the four important language skills, i.e. listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Rahoomi, Dehham, & Al-Wahid 2019).

Table 13 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) for indicators related to the impact of different texts (reading passages) on the reading comprehension skills of the respondents. The mean values offered insights into the average response for each indicator, and the standard deviations indicated the degree of variability in the responses.

Table 13. *Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension Skills of the Respondents in terms of Texts (Reading Passages)*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Texts with interesting story	4.89	.31	Strongly Agree
2. Texts with pictures	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
3. Texts with one's own schemata	4.52	.75	Strongly Agree
4. Texts with good organization and pattern for eyes comfort	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
5. Texts with suitable amount, neither too short nor too long	4.98	.14	Strongly Agree
6. Texts related to a student's own living or previous living environment, cultures, tradition and lifestyles	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
7. Texts with simple grammar and structures	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	4.91	.11	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.50-4.49, Agree; 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree

The highest mean scores were observed for all indicators, including "Texts with pictures" (Mean=5.00), "Texts with good organization and pattern for eyes comfort" (Mean=5.00), "Texts related to a student's own living or previous living environment, cultures, traditions, and lifestyles" (Mean=5.00), "Texts with simple grammar and structures" (Mean=5.00), "Texts with interesting story" (Mean=4.89), and "Texts with suitable amount, neither too short nor too long" (Mean=4.98). These maximum mean scores, coupled with zero standard deviations, suggested unanimous agreement among respondents, expressing a "Strongly Agree" sentiment towards the positive impact of these text characteristics on their reading comprehension skills.

The overall mean for the total measure was 4.91, with a very low standard deviation of 0.11, indicating a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of various text characteristics on their reading comprehension skills.

The implications of these findings were crucial for educators and curriculum designers. The strong agreement on the positive impact of texts with pictures, good organization, relevance to students' lives, simple grammar and structures, interesting stories, and suitable length indicated that these characteristics were highly valued and perceived as effective by the respondents. Educators can use this information to tailor reading materials to better engage students and enhance their comprehension skills. Additionally, recognizing the significance of eye comfort, cultural relevance, and linguistic simplicity in texts can contribute to the development of more accessible and engaging reading materials for diverse learners. Overall, aligning texts with these positive characteristics can create a more enriching and effective reading comprehension learning experience for students.

DepEd Order 45, series of 2002 emphasized the fundamental goal of ensuring that every child has the opportunity to develop proficient reading skills. This initiative underscored the importance of literacy as a foundational skill for academic success and lifelong learning.

Table 14 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) for indicators related to the impact of various environments on the reading comprehension skills of the respondents. The mean values provided insights into the average response for each indicator, and the standard deviations indicated the degree of variability in the responses.

Table 14. *Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension Skills of the Respondents in terms of Environments*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. The expectation of surroundings which encourage a student to be able to read English	4.98	.14	Strongly Agree
2. The importance of reading English given by the society	4.71	.67	Strongly Agree
3. The encouragement of reading English from the family	4.66	.65	Strongly Agree
4. The encouragement of reading English from the school	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
5. Living in the same environment with native speakers	5.00	.00	Strongly Agree
6. Living in the different environment with native speakers	1.42	.88	Strongly Disagree
Total Measure	4.30	.19	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.50-4.49, Agree; 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree

The highest mean scores were observed for indicators such as "Living in the same environment with native speakers" (Mean=5.00), "The encouragement of reading English from the school" (Mean=5.00), "The expectation of surroundings that encouraged a student to

be able to read English" (Mean=4.98), and "The importance of reading English given by the society" (Mean=4.71). These high mean scores, coupled with low standard deviations, suggested a strong consensus among respondents, with the majority expressing a "Strongly Agree" sentiment towards the positive impact of these environmental factors on their reading comprehension skills.

However, "Living in the different environment with native speakers" received a notably lower mean score of 1.42, indicating strong disagreement among respondents regarding the impact of this environment on their reading comprehension skills. The high standard deviation of 0.88 for this indicator indicated variability in responses.

The overall mean for the total measure was 4.30, with a low standard deviation of 0.19, indicating a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the positive impact of various environments on their reading comprehension skills.

The implications of these findings for educators and policymakers were significant. The strong agreement on the positive impact of living in the same environment with native speakers, school encouragement, societal importance, and the expectations of surroundings suggested that these factors contributed significantly to the development of reading comprehension skills. Recognizing and leveraging these positive environmental influences can inform educational strategies and policies aimed at fostering a conducive environment for English language development. Additionally, understanding the strong disagreement regarding living in a different environment with native speakers may prompt further investigation into potential challenges or issues students face in such contexts, guiding the development of more tailored support systems. Overall, aligning educational and societal environments with these positive factors can enhance the effectiveness of reading comprehension instruction.

Based by Ngene et al. (2018), they found that the school's social environment was directly related to academic achievement and that a positive social environment played an important role in developing students' academic abilities.

Table 15. *Consolidated Findings of the Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension Skills of the Respondents*

<i>Components</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learning Preferences	4.30	.30	Agree
Motivation	4.26	.27	Agree
Attitude	4.66	.19	Strongly Agree
Teaching Techniques	4.61	.20	Strongly Agree
Texts (Reading Passages)	4.91	.11	Strongly Agree
Environments (surrounding, society and cultures where the reader lives)	4.30	.19	Agree
Total Measure	4.51	.10	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.50–4.49, Agree; 4.50–5.00, Strongly Agree

Table 15 presents the consolidated findings of various determinants that affected the reading comprehension skills of the respondents. The components included Learning Preferences, Motivation, Attitude, Teaching Techniques, Texts (Reading Passages), and Environments. The mean values provided an overview of the average response for each component, and the standard deviations indicated the degree of variability in the responses.

The highest mean scores were observed for Attitude (Mean=4.66), Texts (Reading Passages) (Mean=4.91), Teaching Techniques (Mean=4.61), and the Total Measure (Mean=4.51). These high mean scores, coupled with low standard deviations, suggested a strong consensus among respondents, with the majority expressing either a "Strongly Agree" or "Agree" sentiment towards the positive impact of these components on their reading comprehension skills. Motivation and Environments received slightly lower mean scores but still fell within the "Agree" range, indicating a general agreement among respondents regarding the positive impact of these factors on reading comprehension skills.

The overall mean for the Total Measure was 4.51, with a very low standard deviation of 0.10, indicating a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the positive impact of the combined factors on their reading comprehension skills.

The implications of these consolidated findings were valuable for educators and curriculum designers. The strong consensus on the positive impact of attitude, teaching techniques, and reading passages indicates that these aspects are critical contributors to effective reading comprehension. Recognizing and leveraging these positive factors can inform the development of instructional strategies and materials that enhanced students' reading comprehension skills. Additionally, understanding the agreement on motivation and environments provided insight into the broader context influencing students' reading abilities. Overall, aligning educational practices and environments with these positive factors can contribute to a more effective and engaging reading comprehension learning experience for students. External factors can be seen from the social environment (Mardika, 2019). The social environment shaped interpersonal relationships, communication dynamics, and opportunities for collaborative learning when combined with external circumstances.

Problem 3: What is the reading comprehension of the respondents?

Table 16 presents the reading comprehension of the respondents categorized by Word Reading Score percentages and corresponding Oral Reading Levels. The Word Reading Score percentages included 97-100 (Independent), 90-96 (Instructional), and Below-89

(Frustration). The table also provided the frequency and percentage distribution for each category.

Table 16. *Reading Comprehension of the Respondents in terms of Word Reading Score*

Word Reading Score (%)	Oral Reading Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
97-100	Independent	6	6.0
90-96	Instructional	35	35.0
Below-89	Frustration	59	59.0
Total		100	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 84.43 (10.08)

The majority of respondents, comprising 59.0%, fell into the Below-89 category, indicating a frustration level in their word reading scores. Another significant portion, 35.0%, fell into the 90-96 range, categorizing them as having instructional reading levels. A smaller percentage, 6.0%, fell into the 97-100 range, indicating an independent reading level. The total sample size was reported as 100 respondents.

The note at the bottom of the table provided additional statistical information, indicating the mean (M) Word Reading Score as 84.43 with a standard deviation (SD) of 10.08. This information offered an average measure of the respondents' word reading scores and the degree of variability within the dataset.

These findings highlighted the distribution of respondents across different levels of word reading proficiency. The majority falling into the frustration category suggested a potential area for targeted intervention and support to enhance word reading skills. The mean and standard deviation provided an overview of the central tendency and variability in the word reading scores, aiding in the interpretation of the overall reading comprehension performance of the surveyed population. Educators and researchers can utilize this information to tailor interventions and instructional strategies based on the identified reading levels, fostering more effective reading comprehension development among students.

According to Caraig and Quimbo (2022), reading comprehension is the ability to define word by word and create a profound idea from the talks given or read. The result showed that students need to enhance their reading skills to improve their reading comprehension.

Table 17. *Reading Comprehension of the Respondents in terms of Comprehension Score*

Comprehension Score (%)	Oral Reading Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
80-100	Independent	24	24.0
59-79	Instructional	30	30.0
Below-58	Frustration	46	46.0
Total		100	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 65.47 (18.26)

Table 17 presents the reading comprehension of the respondents categorized by comprehension score percentages and corresponding oral reading levels. The comprehension score percentages included 80-100 (Independent), 59-79 (Instructional), and Below-58 (Frustration).

The distribution of respondents based on comprehension score revealed that 46.0% fell into the Below-58 range, categorizing them as having frustration-level comprehension scores. Another significant portion, 30.0%, fell into the 59-79 range, indicating instructional-level comprehension. The remaining 24.0% fell into the 80-100 range, representing independent-level comprehension. The note at the bottom of the table provided additional statistical information, indicating the mean (M) Comprehension Score as 65.47 with a standard deviation (SD) of 18.26. This information offered an average measure of the respondents' comprehension scores and the degree of variability within the dataset.

These findings shed light on the distribution of comprehension scores among the surveyed population. The majority of respondents falling into the frustration category suggested a potential area for targeted intervention and support to enhance overall comprehension skills. The mean and standard deviation provided an overview of the central tendency and variability in the comprehension scores, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the respondents' reading comprehension performance.

Reading is one of the four language skills required when the students learn the target. Both English teachers and students need to improve and master the four important language skills, i.e. listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Rahoomi, Dehham, & Al-Wahid, 2019). Being able to read well helped people understand written materials better and improves their language skills in general.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the socio-economic profile and the determinants that affect the reading comprehension skills of the respondents?

Table 18 presents the relationship analysis between the socio-economic profile of the respondents and the determinants influencing their reading comprehension skills. The analysis employed the Point-Biserial Correlation coefficient (r-value) and associated p-values to determine the significance of relationships. Several factors were found to have non-significant relationships with the socio-economic profile of the respondents.

Table 18. *Relationship1 between the Socio-Economic Profile and the Determinants that Affect the Reading Comprehension Skills of the Respondents*

Socio-Economic	Factors		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Age			
Below-20	-.137	.173	Not significant
21-40	.130	.196	Not significant
41-above	.001	.992	Not significant
Gender (Male)	-.023	.817	Not significant
Parents' Occupation			
Farmer	-.028	.780	Not significant
Construction Worker	.049	.625	Not significant
Vendor	-.086	.392	Not significant
OFW	.132	.191	Not significant
Marital Status			
Married	-.013	.898	Not significant
Single	-.049	.630	Not significant
Widow	.217*	.030	Significant
Grade Level			
Grade 7	.193	.055	Not significant
Grade 8	-.131	.193	Not significant
Grade 9	-.106	.296	Not significant
Occupation			
Farmer	.055	.589	Not significant
Housewife	-.090	.374	Not significant
Construction Worker	.180	.073	Not significant
Student	-.128	.206	Not significant

Note: 1based on Point-Biserial Correlation Not significant ($p > .05$) *significant at .05 level

For age, there was no significant correlation found for any age group, including those below 20 years, between 21 and 40 years, and 41 years and above. Similarly, sex did not exhibit a significant correlation with reading comprehension skills. Regarding parents' occupation, no significant correlation was observed for individuals with parents working as farmers, construction workers, vendors, or Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs). Marital status, grade level, and occupation also did not show significant correlations with reading comprehension skills.

However, there were notable exceptions. The marital status of widows exhibited a significant positive correlation with reading comprehension skills among of the three category of marital status it showed it has biggest r-value which is 0.217 and the lowest p-value which is 0.030. This suggested that widows may have higher reading comprehension skills compared to other marital status categories.

While several relationships were found to be not significant, it was important to consider the context and potential influencing determinants that might not have been captured in this analysis. For instance, socio-economic factors beyond those assessed in this study may contribute to the observed non-significant relationships. Additionally, individual differences and external factors not included in the analysis might play a role in shaping reading comprehension skills.

Educationally, these findings emphasized the need for a more holistic understanding of factors influencing reading comprehension skills. A focus on diverse socio-economic backgrounds, individual learning preferences, and external factors may provide a more comprehensive view. Targeted interventions and support systems should be designed considering the unique needs of different groups, such as widows, who may exhibit distinct patterns in reading comprehension skills.

According to Caraig and Quimbo (2022), proficient comprehension skills are crucial in various aspects of life, from academic success to professional development, as they empower individuals to process and utilize information effectively across diverse contexts.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the socio-economic profile and the reading comprehension skills of the respondents?

Table 19 illustrates the relationship analysis between the socio-economic profile of respondents and their word reading skills, employing the Point-Biserial Correlation coefficient (r-value) and associated p-values. The findings revealed that for various socio-economic factors, there were no significant correlations observed with word reading skills.

Age groups, including Below-20, 21-40, and 41-above, showed non-significant correlations, indicating that age did not have a significant impact on word reading skills in this context. Similarly, sex, parents' occupation (farmer, construction worker, vendor, OFW), marital status, grade level (Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9), and occupation (farmer, housewife, construction worker, student) did not exhibit significant correlations with word reading skills.

Table 19. Relationship1 between the Socio-Economic Profile and the Word Reading Skills of the Respondents

	<i>Socio-Economic</i>	<i>Word Reading Skills</i>		<i>Remarks</i>
		<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Age				
	Below-20	.004	.968	Not significant
	21-40	.092	.363	Not significant
	41-above	-.138	.171	Not significant
Sex (Male)		.153	.129	Not significant
Parents' Occupation				
	Farmer	.105	.299	Not significant
	Construction Worker	.077	.444	Not significant
	Vendor	-.195	.052	Not significant
	OFW	-.095	.346	Not significant
Marital Status				
	Married	.073	.468	Not significant
	Single	-.030	.770	Not significant
	Widow	-.156	.122	Not significant
Grade Level				
	Grade 7	.063	.535	Not significant
	Grade 8	-.071	.481	Not significant
	Grade 9	.004	.967	Not significant
Occupation				
	Farmer	.175	.081	Not significant
	Housewife	-.067	.505	Not significant
	Construction Worker	-.082	.416	Not significant
	Student	-.046	.649	Not significant

Note: 1Based on Point-Biserial Correlation Not significant ($p > .05$)

While the majority of the relationships were not significant, it is crucial to consider potential external factors or nuanced aspects that were not included in the analysis. Additionally, the non-significant relationships highlighted the complexity of the relationship between socio-economic factors and word reading skills, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive understanding that goes beyond the variables considered in this study.

Educationally, these findings suggested that word reading skills may be influenced by a combination of factors beyond those explored in this analysis. A more detailed exploration of individual learning preferences, additional socio-economic indicators, and external factors could provide a more nuanced understanding. The absence of significant relationships also underscored the importance of personalized and inclusive instructional approaches that cater to the diverse needs of students.

Good word reading skills are one of the most critical skills required for effective comprehension of written material by Joseph (2018). There are a lot of factors that affect the reading skills of the students the socio-economic and the external factors should be considered in making intervention given by the teacher.

Table 20 outlines the relationship analysis between the socio-economic profile of the respondents and their comprehension skills, utilizing the Point-Biserial Correlation coefficient (r -value) and corresponding p -values. The findings revealed that, across various socio-economic factors, there were no significant correlations observed with comprehension skills.

The age groups, including Below-20, 21-40, and 41-above, demonstrated non-significant correlations with comprehension skills. Similarly, sex, parents' occupation (farmer, construction worker, vendor, OFW), marital status, grade level (Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9), and occupation (farmer, housewife, construction worker, student) did not exhibit significant correlations with comprehension skills.

Although the majority of relationships were not significant, it was crucial to consider potential external factors or nuanced aspects that were not included in the analysis.

The non-significant relationships underscored the intricate nature of the relationship between socio-economic factors and comprehension skills, highlighting the need for a more comprehensive understanding that extends beyond the variables examined in this study.

Educationally, these findings suggested that comprehension skills may be influenced by a combination of factors beyond those explored in this analysis. A more detailed exploration of individual learning preferences, additional socio-economic indicators, and external factors could provide a more nuanced understanding. The absence of significant relationships also emphasized the importance of personalized and inclusive instructional approaches that cater to the diverse needs of students.

Socioeconomic status (SES) may indirectly influence many factors relevant for reading outcomes, including a student's access to educational resources, early literacy experiences, language exposure, academic skills and resources, and psychological correlates (Romeo, Uchida, & Christodolou, 2022).

Table 20. Relationship2 between the Socio-Economic Profile and the Comprehension Skills of the Respondents

Socio-Economic	Comprehension Skills		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Age			
Below-20	.087	.388	Not significant
21-40	-.083	.414	Not significant
41-above	-.001	.993	Not significant
Sex (Male)	.102	.313	Not significant
Parents' Occupation			
Farmer	.096	.341	Not significant
Construction Worker	-.021	.833	Not significant
Vendor	-.084	.409	Not significant
OFW	-.034	.740	Not significant
Marital Status			
Married	-.073	.470	Not significant
Single	.091	.365	Not significant
Widow	-.063	.536	Not significant
Grade Level			
Grade 7	-.023	.823	Not significant
Grade 8	-.001	.994	Not significant
Grade 9	.034	.736	Not significant
Occupation			
Farmer	.017	.867	Not significant
Housewife	-.050	.619	Not significant
Construction Worker	-.039	.703	Not significant
Student	.089	.376	Not significant

Note: 1based on Point-Biserial Correlation

Not significant (p>.05)

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between the determinants that affect the reading comprehension and the reading comprehension skills of the respondents?

Table 21 presents the relationship analysis between determinants influencing reading comprehension and word reading skills, utilizing the Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) and corresponding p-values. The findings indicated that, across various factors, there were no significant correlations observed with word reading skills.

For Learning preferences, motivation, attitude, teaching techniques, texts (reading passages), environments, and the total measure, the r-values ranged from -.008 to .111, and all associated p-values were greater than 0.05, indicating non-significant relationships.

Table 21. Relationship3 between the Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension and the Word Reading Skills of the Respondents

Determinants	Word Reading Skills		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Learning Preferences	.111	.270	Not significant
Motivation	.004	.965	Not significant
Attitude	.044	.664	Not significant
Teaching Techniques	.042	.678	Not significant
Texts (Reading Passages)	-.062	.543	Not significant
Environments (surrounding, society and cultures where the reader lives)	-.008	.936	Not significant
Total Measure	.072	.479	Not significant

Note: 2based on Pearson Correlation

Not significant (p>.05)

While the lack of significant correlations implied that these factors may not directly impact word reading skills, it was essential to recognize the complexity of reading development and the potential influence of other variables not considered in this analysis. Additionally, individual differences and external factors not included in the study may play a role in shaping word reading skills.

These findings suggested that the relationship between factors influencing reading comprehension and word reading skills may not be straightforward. The absence of significant correlations highlighted the need for a more nuanced understanding of how various factors interact in the development of different aspects of reading skills. Future research could explore additional variables and their potential impact on the relationship between these factors, contributing to the development of more comprehensive and effective literacy interventions.

DepEd Order no. 013, series of 2023, stressed that to meet the various learning requirements of all students, specialized interventions and focused support systems are being developed to make sure that no kid is left behind.

Table 22. Relationship between the Determinants that Affect Reading Comprehension and the Comprehension Skills of the Respondents

Determinants	Comprehension Skills		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Learning Preferences	-.082	.416	Not significant
Motivation	.049	.630	Not significant
Attitude	.039	.703	Not significant
Teaching Techniques	.092	.363	Not significant
Texts (Reading Passages)	.105	.300	Not significant
Environments (surrounding, society and cultures where the reader lives)	-.025	.801	Not significant
Total Measure	.035	.731	Not significant

Note: Based on Pearson Correlation

Not significant ($p > .05$)

Table 22 reveals the relationship analysis between determinants influencing reading comprehension and the comprehension skills of the respondents, utilizing the Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) and corresponding p-values. The results revealed that, across various factors, there were no significant correlations observed with comprehension skills.

For Learning preferences, motivation, attitude, teaching techniques, texts (reading passages), environments, and the total measure, the r-values ranged from -.082 to .105, and all associated p-values were greater than 0.05, indicating non-significant relationships.

The absence of significant correlations implied that these factors may not have a direct impact on comprehension skills, at least in the context of this study. However, it was crucial to recognize that reading comprehension is a multifaceted skill influenced by various factors, and the non-significant results may be due to the complexity of these relationships.

From an educational perspective, these findings suggested that the relationship between factors influencing reading comprehension and actual comprehension skills may be more intricate than initially assumed. The lack of significant correlations highlighted the need for a comprehensive approach to understand and improve comprehension skills, considering individual differences and the interplay of various factors.

Action plan that are needed to address these comprehension mistakes, such as providing clear teaching in comprehension techniques and creating a reading environment that promotes critical thinking and active involvement with the text (Fauzi, 2018).

Problem 7: What action plan for students can be formulated based on the result of the study?

Based on the result of the study, the respondents fall into frustration level of reading comprehension. This should be addressed by the teacher which they are going to give differentiated activities. They should manifest praises which help to encourage the learners to love reading. The researcher proposed the program Enhancing Literacy Excellence (ELE): Tailored Strategies for Reading Success. This is to help learners to improve reading proficiency and reduce reading difficulties.

Proposed Title: Enhancing Literacy Excellence (ELE) Program: Tailored Strategies for Reading Success

Rationale

The "Enhancing Literacy Excellence (ELE) Program" has been designed to address the multifaceted challenges identified in the recent study on students' reading comprehension and word reading skills. The program employs a strategic blend of tailored reading materials, individualized instruction, and motivational strategies to create an inclusive and engaging learning environment. By recognizing the diverse learning preferences, socio-economic factors, and motivational triggers uncovered in the study, the ELE Program aims to cultivate a culture of literacy excellence.

The integration of these targeted interventions seeks to not only enhance students' reading skills but also foster a lifelong love for reading, thereby laying a strong foundation for their academic and personal success. The ELE Program emphasizes the importance of personalized learning, acknowledging that each student's journey to literacy excellence is unique, and thus, requires a tailored and comprehensive approach. Through this program, we aim to empower students with the skills and motivation necessary for sustained reading success and academic achievement.

Conclusions

The study's comprehensive exploration of factors influencing reading comprehension skills has yielded valuable insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers. The strong consensus among respondents regarding the positive impact of attitude, texts, teaching techniques, and the overall learning environment on reading comprehension emphasized the importance of cultivating a positive and engaging atmosphere. This underscored the need for tailored instructional strategies that addressed individual learning preferences and emphasized the significance of fostering a positive attitude toward reading. The slightly lower mean scores for motivation and environments suggested that while these factors were still perceived positively, there may be room for additional support or interventions to enhance their influence on students' reading comprehension skills. Therefore, initiatives that incorporated

motivational elements and created supportive reading environments could be beneficial for further enhancing these aspects.

Furthermore, the distribution of respondents across different word reading and comprehension score categories revealed the diverse proficiency levels within the sample. The majority of students falling into frustration and instructional levels indicated a need for targeted interventions aimed at improving foundational reading skills. Tailoring interventions to address specific challenges identified in the study, such as word reading difficulties, can contribute to more effective literacy programs. In conclusion, the study advocated for a holistic approach to literacy education, considering individual preferences, attitudes, and the broader learning environment, to foster a lifelong love for reading and equip students with the skills necessary for academic and personal success.

The findings from the relationship analysis between the socio-economic profile of respondents and factors influencing their reading comprehension skills highlighted predominantly non-significant correlations across various demographic factors. Age groups, sex, parents' occupation, marital status, grade level, and occupation did not demonstrate significant relationships with reading comprehension skills, except for a significant positive correlation found among widowed individuals. This exception suggested a unique association between widowhood and higher reading comprehension skills. Despite non-significant relationships for most variables, the study emphasized the need to consider contextual and unmeasured factors that could influence reading comprehension skills. These findings underscored the complexity of the relationship between socio-economic profiles and reading comprehension, urging a nuanced understanding for effective intervention strategies.

Similarly, the relationship analysis between the socio-economic profile of respondents and their word reading skills revealed non-significant correlations across various factors. Age groups, sex, parents' occupation, marital status, grade level, and occupation did not exhibit significant associations with word reading skills. The analysis for comprehension skills also demonstrated non-significant correlations, emphasizing the intricate nature of the connection between socio-economic factors and both word reading and comprehension skills. These findings underlined the importance of a comprehensive understanding that considered potential external factors or nuanced aspects not included in the analysis, urging educators and policymakers to adopt holistic approaches in addressing literacy challenges.

Thus, the relationship analysis between factors influencing reading comprehension and word reading skills unveiled non-significant correlations. Learning preferences, motivation, attitude, teaching techniques, texts (reading passages), environments, and the total measure did not show significant relationships with word reading skills. The same pattern was observed for comprehension skills. These findings suggested that, within the scope of this study, these factors may not directly impact word reading and comprehension skills. However, the complexity of reading development and the potential influence of unexplored variables must be acknowledged. These results emphasize the need for continued exploration and a holistic understanding of the multifaceted nature of reading skills to inform effective literacy interventions.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

The students foster a positive attitude towards reading by exploring diverse genres and topics that genuinely interest you. Take advantage of available resources, such as engaging reading materials and online platforms, to supplement classroom learning. Develop personalized learning preferences and be proactive in seeking support from teachers or peers when facing challenges. Set realistic reading goals, celebrate small achievements, and understand that reading is a lifelong skill that evolves with practice and curiosity.

For the teachers, it implements a variety of teaching techniques that cater to different learning preferences, ensuring a dynamic and inclusive classroom environment. Incorporate motivational strategies, like recognizing individual achievements and providing constructive feedback, to enhance students' engagement with reading. Continuously explore and incorporate diverse reading materials, including those relevant to students' cultural backgrounds, to make the learning experience more relatable and enjoyable.

For the guidance counsellors, it offers support and guidance to students who may be facing challenges in reading comprehension or word reading skills. Implement targeted interventions for specific groups, such as widowed individuals, based on the identified correlations. Collaborate with teachers to identify effective strategies for promoting a positive attitude towards reading and addressing socio-economic factors that may influence literacy outcomes.

For school administrators, it allocates resources for the development and maintenance of well-equipped libraries with a diverse range of reading materials. Consider organizing literacy-focused events, book clubs, or reading programs to create a reading culture within the school community. Support professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their teaching techniques and strategies for addressing diverse learning preferences.

For the community, it promotes community-wide literacy initiatives, such as book drives, reading workshops, or partnerships with local libraries. Encourage a supportive environment for literacy at home by fostering a love for reading among family members. Collaborate with schools to organize community events that celebrate and showcase the importance of literacy.

For curriculum planners, it reviews and updates the curriculum to incorporate diverse reading materials that align with students' interests, cultural backgrounds, and societal contexts. Integrate literacy-focused modules that emphasize the development of positive attitudes, effective teaching techniques, and motivational strategies.

For future researchers, this study builds by exploring additional socio-economic factors that may influence reading comprehension and word reading skills. Consider longitudinal studies to observe the long-term impact of interventions and changes in socio-economic circumstances on literacy outcomes. Investigate the potential influence of external factors, such as technology use and socio-cultural dynamics, on reading proficiency.

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